

OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

ANNUAL REPORT 21/22

OAD

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The content in this publication is based on OAD project reports, quarterly reports, press releases, and published articles. Activity images are courtesy of the OAD projects.

Design: www.epicreative.co.za

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HIGHLIGHTS

SECOND EXTERNAL REVIEW OF THE OAD COMPLETED

The second external review of the Office of Astronomy for Development was conducted in 2021.

The objective of the review panel was to evaluate the performance of the OAD for the period 1 April 2014 to 31 March 2020 and to make recommendations to optimise the future development of the OAD. Initially delayed by the COVID-19 pandemic, a panel of three experts was constituted to evaluate the OAD: 1. Prof. Ian Corbett (Convener), European Southern Observatory (retired) and past General Secretary of the International Astronomical Union, 2. Prof. Daya Reddy, University of Cape Town, South Africa and President of the International Science Council (2018-2021), and 3. Prof. You-Hua Chu, Academia Sinica Institute of Astronomy and Astrophysics, Taiwan.

As per their terms of reference, the panel members read and analysed relevant documents such as strategic plans, agreements, annual reports, business plans as well as the report from the 2015 external review of the OAD. The OAD website served as an essential reference for projects and activities. This was followed by interviews and written input from a number of stakeholders including the OAD team, steering committee, other IAU Offices, OAD principals- the International Astronomical Union (IAU), the South African National Research Foundation (NRF), and the Department of

Science and Innovation (DSI), host South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO), regional offices, partners, and project leaders.

Overall, the panel provided a glowing evaluation stating that the OAD has turned the somewhat abstract concept of "astronomy for development" into a reality. The review panel commended the OAD for providing the astronomy community with an effective focus and conduit for its engagement in socio-economic development. The panel further recommended that the OAD continue at the SAAO under its current arrangements with major efforts made to increase resources for the Flagships and Regional Offices.

OAD AT THE IAU GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The XXXI IAU General Assembly (IAUGA2022) is scheduled to take place from 2–11 August 2022 in Busan, South Korea as a hybrid meeting. The OAD will be organising sessions on 'Astronomy for Development' (five sessions over two days). The OAD will also share an exhibition space at the conference with the IAU and other Offices.

In his talk at the virtual Business sessions organised in 2021, OAD Director Kevin Govender appealed to the IAU membership, communicators, educators, and the larger astronomy community to join hands with the OAD, contributing their skills and time to create a better world for all. He said, "The global pandemic has highlighted the great challenges of our time and the inequalities that persist. The OAD is a place for people to come together and tackle these challenges by

applying the sophistication and grandeur of astronomy." The OAD offers various ways for individuals and organisations to collaborate, including internships, fellowships, partnerships, and regional offices. Get in touch with us or find us at the IAU exhibition (physical or virtual) to discuss possible ways to contribute and collaborate.

INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF BASIC SCIENCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN 2022

The International Astronomical Union is one of several scientific unions and institutions that are coordinating the International Year of Basic Sciences for Sustainable Development (IYBSSD) in 2022, to promote the links between the basic sciences and the Sustainable Development Goals.

We need more basic sciences to achieve Agenda 2030 and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals. This was the message from the United Nations (UN) General Assembly on 2 December 2021 when Member States approved, by consensus, resolution 76/A/L.12, promulgating 2022 as the International Year of Basic Sciences for Sustainable Development.

The IAU has long recognised the roles of basic sciences for sustainable development. Through the dedicated Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD), established in partnership with the South African National Research Foundation and Department of Science and Innovation, the IAU actively supports activities around the globe that further the use of astronomy, including its practitioners, skills and infrastructures, as a tool for sustainable development. To mark IYBSSD, the OAD introduced 'Basic Sciences for Sustainable Development' as a theme in its 2022 call for astronomy-for-development proposals.

The UN resolution 'invites all [its] Member States, organisations of the United Nations system and other global, regional and subregional organisations, as well as other relevant stakeholders, including academia, civil society, inter alia, international and national nongovernmental organisations, individuals and the private sector, to observe and raise awareness of the importance of basic sciences for sustainable development, in accordance with national priorities'.

The decision of the UN General Assembly was motivated by 'the high value of basic sciences for humankind', and the fact that 'enhanced global awareness of, and increased education in the basic sciences is vital to attain sustainable development and to improve the quality of life for people all over the world'. It also stressed that 'basic sciences and emerging technologies respond to the needs of humankind by providing access to information and increasing the health and wellbeing of individuals, communities, and societies'. The successes and difficulties of the global fight against the COVID-19 pandemic have been for two years a stark reminder of the importance of basic sciences.

IYBSSD2022 events and activities will be organised around the world until 30 June 2023. Over 90 national and international science academies, learned societies, scientific networks, research and education centers are supporting this initiative. They will organise events and activities all over the planet during the year to showcase and improve the links between basic sciences and the 17 SDGs.

OAD FELLOWS

The OAD is indebted to the global astronomy community that lead projects and activities, as well as contribute in several ways to the OAD's mission. Since the pandemic, the OAD Fellowship programme offers an option to join the team remotely. In the past year, several remote Fellows have joined the OAD team.

ARMINE PATATANYAN, SANDRA BENITEZ, DOMINIC VERTUE

Armine, Sandra, and Dominic are working on the OAD's Astronomy for Mental Health project that aims to explore how the inspirational and cultural aspects of astronomy can help improve mental well-being of vulnerable groups. They are working in collaboration with astronomers, psychologists, mental health professionals, social workers and other specialists, focusing initial efforts in Armenia, Spain, and South Africa (the countries where they are based).

Armine has a background in International Relations, Human Rights and Conflict Management. Dominic has a background in Social Work and humanitarian assistance with a master's in medical social work. Sandra is an astronomer at the European Space Astronomy Centre of the European Space Agency.

DANA FICUT-VICAS, MARIA ALEJANDRA DIAZ

Dana and Alejandra are studying past OAD projects to evaluate the multi-dimensional contribution of funded projects to sustainable development. They are performing qualitative analysis, using feedback collected through interviews with project coordinators. And they are also analysing the hard results from projects, such as reports and other deliverables, to determine quantitative outcomes. Dana is an astronomer captivated by the idea of using astronomy to make the world better. Alejandra recently earned her Master's in astronomy from the Autónoma University of Madrid and will soon start her PhD in astrophysics.

TAWANDA CHINGOZHA

Tawanda comes from a development background and plays an 'all-rounder' role at the OAD. He advises on projects and activities to improve their outcomes and impact. He is currently working to establish partnerships between the OAD and the development community. Development challenges are multi-faceted and require multi-stakeholder approaches. Tawanda believes that collaborative work will pay more dividends - natural scientists bring technical skills and technologies that society requires while social scientists ensure more effective engagement with communities. He has created a free course on "Introduction to Development Economics for Non-Social Scientists". The course decomposes many development challenges into several causes/reasons and provides hints on what science professionals can do to change the status quo. The course is delivered in workshop format and also available online for anyone to read.

NIKHITA MADHANPALL

Nikhita Madhanpall leads the Big Data Hackathon project in partnership with DARA (Development in Africa with Radio Astronomy) Big Data and the Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy (IDIA). The hackathons aim to provide exposure to skills such as data science and machine learning that are commonly used in astronomy, and provide participants with the confidence to pursue studies or careers in the field of data science going forward.

Nikhita has a background in astronomy and has worked as part of the RFI team at the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory.

TOM MUTABAZI

Tom Mutabazi is a researcher at the Mbarara University of Science and Technology in Uganda. He is applying his astronomy skills, such as scripting and programming skills, and also more discipline-specific skills like knowledge of passbands, matching images of differing resolutions, understanding of coordinate systems and image mosaicking, big data handling, cloud computing, in remote sensing work. He is using Google's cloud computing infrastructure (Google Earth Engine) which allows planetary-scale geospatial analysis. Current work involves calculations of water turbidity index using red and green bands, time series analysis of NDVI changes. Long term plans include vegetation classification to assess land-use and land-cover patterns, model predictions (empirical models), and engaging partners such as the National Forestry Authority, Ministry of Water and Environment, National Environmental Management Authority.

Armine Patatanyan

Sandra Benitez

Dominic Vertue

Dana Ficut-Vicas

Maria Alejandra Diaz

Tawanda Chingoza

Nikhita Madhanpall

Tom Mutabazi

NEW MEMBERS ON OAD STEERING COMMITTEE AND REVIEW PANEL

The OAD welcomed several new members to its Steering Committee. The committee exercises general oversight of the activities of the OAD and its staff. It comprises three members nominated by the IAU and three members nominated by the NRF.

SOLOMON TESSEMA (CHAIR): Dr. Solomon Tessema is a past Director General of the Ethiopian Space Science and Technology Institute and Vice president of the International Astronomical Union.

DIANA WORRALL: Prof. Diana Worrall is Emeritus Professor, School of Physics at the University of Bristol. She is the Assistant General Secretary of the International Astronomical Union.

DANIELA LAZZARO: Prof. Daniela Lazzaro is an astronomer at the Observatorio Nacional. She is a Vice-President of the International Astronomical Union Executive Committee and Organising Committee Member of the Executive Committee Working group on Women in Astronomy.

DAYA REDDY: Prof. Daya Reddy holds the South African Research Chair in Computational Mechanics at the University of Cape Town, South Africa. He held the position of inaugural president of the International Science Council from 2018-2021.

DELIA MARSHALL: Prof. Delia Marshall is a professor in the Department of Physics at the University of the Western Cape, South Africa. Her research interest is in undergraduate physics education and higher education studies.

MMANTSAE MOCHE DIALE: Prof. Mmantsae Moche Diale is Professor of Physics and holds the South African Research Chair (SARCHI) on Clean and Green Energy at the Department of Physics, University of Pretoria. She serves as an expert on several national and international committees, boards and initiatives for renewable energy solutions and related matters in climate change.

The OAD also added several members to its project review panel. The panel consists of experts who give their time voluntarily and evaluate the applications submitted to the OAD Annual Call for Proposals. They are selected on the basis of their skills, prior knowledge, experience, geographic locations, gender and cultural diversity.

Solomon Tessema

Diana Worrall

Daniela Lazzaro

Daya Reddy

Delia Marshall

Mmantsae Moche Diale

CELEBRATING A DECADE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

The OAD completed 10 years of existence in 2021!

The OAD was inaugurated back in April 2011 by the South African Minister of Science and Technology in the presence of partners, supporters, and contributors to our vision of 'Astronomy for a better world'. Since then, our family has grown all around the world. Thanks to this global family and our small team, we can proudly declare that the OAD now has 11 Regional Offices, and has benefited people in more than 100 countries through its 200 projects.

“Congratulation on 10 years of OAD! And a sincere thanks for the enthusiasm, dedication and for all the work done.”

PROF. TERESA LAGO

IAU General Secretary

“The establishment of OAD has made a paradigm shift for the development of astronomy in developing countries. We have to maintain the past achievements of OAD and move forward for more success.”

DR. SOLOMON TESSEMA

*Chair of OAD Steering Committee,
and Past Director General, Ethiopian Space Science
and Technology Institute*

“Well done on a decadal journey of success.”

TAKALANI NEMAUNGANI

*Chief Director: Astronomy, Department of
Science and Innovation*

PUBLICATIONS

COVID-19 BUDGET PRESSURES THREATEN CURIOSITY-DRIVEN SCIENCE. THAT'S A BAD THING.

OAD's Dr. Vanessa McBride published an article in *The Conversation* on the importance of curiosity-driven sciences like astronomy. She writes: "The pandemic has underscored that the world requires agility for survival. That makes blue skies science – which encourages curiosity and nimble thinking – perhaps more important than ever. But this will require a long-term view from governments and funders, particularly by providing decades of funding and freedom to allow scientists to ask the "why?" questions."

ASTROSTAYS: CREATING SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS THROUGH COMMUNITY-LED ASTRO-TOURISM – WTTC TRAVEL HUB

Sonal Asgotraa, project manager of Astrostays, wrote about community-led tourism models to support livelihoods in a post-pandemic world.

Astrostays was also featured in the *Unlocking Science* series by the International Science Council, published by BBC Storyworks.

THE COSMOAMAUTAS PROJECT FOR EQUITABLE SCIENTIFIC EDUCATION IN PERU

Equitable and high-quality scientific education is essential for fighting social inequalities and misinformation. The CosmoAmautas project, funded by the OAD, aims to address this need and use astronomy to contribute to an accessible and decentralised scientific education in Peru. They published an article in the journal *Nature Astronomy*.

PROJECTS

ANNUAL CALL FOR PROPOSALS

The IAU is funding 17 projects around the world through the OAD call for proposals. These projects will address various socio-economic and sustainable-development challenges using astronomy-related interventions.

The selected initiatives include a community-empowerment project in Nepal; school- and university-level astronomy interventions in Ghana, South Africa and Nigeria; astro-tourism projects in Mongolia, the US Virgin islands, India and Tanzania; an educational project for displaced children in Burkina Faso; virtual mentorship programmes in Colombia and Central America and Caribbean countries; teacher training programmes in Malaysia and Peru and more.

This was the OAD's tenth annual call for proposals, and 97 applications were received at stage 1, from which 41 were selected for stage 2. An independent review panel of experts in the fields of astronomy and development evaluated the applications and chose 17 projects, which were later approved by the OAD Steering Committee.

The annual call for proposals is open to anyone from anywhere in the world. Through it, the IAU has granted more than €1,000,000 to 200 projects since 2011, reaching people in more than 100 countries.

LIST OF PROJECTS FUNDED, IN ALPHABETICAL ORDER:

1. A virtual community mentorship programme for development in Colombia
2. Acornhoek Physics Summer School
3. Astro3DBol— Archeoastronomy Teaching Kit in Bolivia
4. Astrolab 2022
5. Astronomy for community empowerment in Nepal
6. Astronomy in Ghana
7. Astronomy training outreach for preschool teachers in Malaysia through service-learning approach
8. Astro-tourism development in Tanzania
9. Astro-tourism with nomadic herder in forest area of Mongolia
10. Beyond the Beach: Foundations for Caribbean Astro-tourism
11. Bringing radio astronomy to classrooms with affordable radio telescopes
12. Cenca Bridge
13. CosmoAmautas: Virtual teacher training in vulnerable regions in Peru
14. Education for All: promoting education in internally displaced communities in Burkina Faso
15. Guide training workshop for tribal students
16. Mobile Astronomy Village
17. SciGirls – Empowering girls in science through astronomy

The OAD has also compiled a list of recommended proposals that were approved by the reviewers but could not be funded. You can browse through the Recommended list and contact us for more details or to support one or more projects.

UPDATES FROM PROJECTS

LEVERAGING LOCAL ASTRONOMY SITE TO PROMOTE STEM, MADAGASCAR

A team of female scientists from Ikala STEM (Women in STEM – Madagascar) implemented LAMPS, a project to directly address the inequality between urban and rural Madagascar in accessing quality STEM education, and to showcase the relevance of science in everyday life. Originally planned to be held in the AVN (African VLBI Network) host city of Arivonimamo, this OAD-funded project was adapted to a two-stage STEM education hybrid event, a one-week online activity (e-LAMPS) and school visits by LAMPS volunteers, due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

REDISCOVERING IDENTITY THROUGH ASTRONOMY, CHILE

The Rediscovering Identity Through Astronomy (RITA) project is using astronomy as a means of common humanitarian awareness, to help indigenous students rediscover ancestral roots. During the project, students, with the help of their teachers, identify with their ancestral roots and indigenous culture through the exploration of worldviews. RITA hopes to increase the interest of indigenous students in STEM careers. The project, conducted by Fundación Janequeo, is working with indigenous educators and students in the Likan Antai, Pascuense and Mapuche communities in Chile.

EMPOWERING RATIONAL CAPACITY THROUGH ASTRONOMY, INDONESIA

Bosscha Observatory, Indonesia coordinates this project to provide distant learning material and methodology to assist teachers, particularly in empowering rational thinking capacity through astronomy. The learning material is enriched with other STEAM topics, most importantly energy, water, and the need to care for Earth. Several online workshops were organised for teachers and online astronomy classes for schools all over Indonesia, with the overall aim of empowering rational thinking through astronomy. Virtual public nights were also conducted at the observatory, with carefully choreographed talks combined with observational activities.

DIY UNIVERSE: A VIRTUAL SCIENCE PROGRAMME FOR SUMMER ENGAGEMENT, UNITED STATES

Families rely on summer programmes to provide enriching experiences, a supportive community, and to address gaps in learning. Due to social distancing constraints during the summer of 2020, youth faced months of unfocused, unstructured time during which it was expected that learning gaps would expand between those whose families were able to provide alternative enriching activities and those whose families could not. This virtual summer programme was intended to provide youth with a quality learning environment that they would not otherwise have. In July 2020, the Christa McAuliffe Center for Integrated Science Learning facilitated a 4-week virtual summer programme with 27 girls enrolled in the Girls Inc. Eureka! STEM programme in Worcester, Massachusetts. The foundation of the programme was DIY Universe, a web-based programme developed by the McAuliffe Center for implementation at Out-of-School Time sites. This programme was offered at no cost to participants.

AMANAR 2.0: A REFUGE IN THE STARS, ALGERIA, SPAIN

The Amanar 2.0 project is educating and inspiring the Sahrawi population using astronomy as well as recording their traditional astronomy knowledge. Amanar 2.0 is a follow-up of the 2019 Amanar: Under the Same Sky project, both funded by the IAU OAD. It is an initiative to stimulate teachers, support schools, and provide inspiration through astronomy in the Sahrawi refugee camps of Tindouf, Algeria. Previously, the project team visited the camps in 2019, conducting teacher training and astronomy activities at schools. Amanar works in tandem with the Vacation in Peace program, through which Sahrawi children visit the Canary Islands and stay with host families for a summer. Unfortunately, when the global pandemic struck, the vacation programme was paused, as well as any visits to the camps by the project team.

Amanar 2.0 includes an ethnoastronomy study to record and disseminate the traditional astronomy knowledge of the Sahrawi population. Five Sahrawi researchers are conducting interviews with elders on their knowledge of the sky and culture related to the stars.

ELIMISHA MSICHANA ELIMISHA JAMII NA ASTRONOMIA, KENYA

In Kenya, although 70.4% of girls (15-19yrs) achieve some sort of primary education, only 4.5% complete secondary education (World Bank, 2012). Only 3.5% of women (aged 15+) have completed tertiary education (World Bank, 2015). This is due to various socio-economic challenges such as teenage pregnancies, early marriages, female genital mutilation, and poverty. Rural areas lack outreach, leadership & mentorship programmes at the key primary-to-secondary transition where dropout rates are high. The Elimisha Msichana Elimisha Jamii na Astronomia (EMEJA) project, Swahili for 'educate a girl child, educate the entire community with Astronomy' or society benefits when a girl is educated, supported by funding from the IAU OAD, is addressing these issues in rural Kenya via outreach programmes, mentorship, and targeted Astro-STEM workshops and scholarships opportunities, guided and supported by long-term student tracking and monitoring.

CODE LEARNING WITH ASTRONOMICAL IDEAS, PORTUGAL, MOZAMBIQUE, TIMOR-LESTE

The IAU Office of Astronomy for Development is supporting the Planetário – Casa da Ciência de Braga, Portugal to develop a code learning programme with the Portuguese School of Mozambique and the Portuguese School of Dili Ruy Cinatti in Timor-Leste. The CODELASTRO project is a code learning programme based on microbits and astronomical topics. The project team, based at the Planetário – Casa da Ciência de Braga in Portugal has partnered with schools in Mozambique and Timor-Leste.

CODELASTRO uses Micro:bit, a pocket programmable device that allows children and young people to learn how to programme in a simple, playful and creative way. Its integrated sensors (buttons, compass, accelerometer, temperature, brightness, Bluetooth connection, LED matrix) allow the development of STEM projects, in which children and young people, almost autonomously and in groups, can learn and lead all phases of design, development, programming and execution.

ASTROLOGOS: STORIES OF THE HISTORY OF THE UNIVERSE, ITALY

"Astrologos" is a science-art project funded by the OAD that revolves around the recording of five short stories by world-renowned writer Italo Calvino, taken from the book 'Cosmicomics', inspired by astronomical facts, and commented on by several astronomers. The recordings, accompanied by original soundtracks and drawings, are publicly available online (Italian). The project hopes to remind the listener of the importance of maintaining perspective and faith in human collaboration, both through scientific inquiry, as well as the arts.

FLAGSHIP UPDATES

FLAGSHIP 1

ASTRONOMY FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

This Flagship aims to use an astronomical facility, such as an observatory or planetarium, as a “hub” to stimulate various socio-economic benefits for the local community. Benefits could include job creation through astronomy-related tourism; community skills development; educational programmes; stimulation of local innovation; alternative activities for youth in order to keep away from negative/harmful activities; and infrastructure development.

COSMOHUB: A NEW INITIATIVE BY ASTROSTAYS

The Astrostays project has launched a unique women-led astrotourism initiative in India called the Cosmohub. Operated by a local women’s group at a monastery in northern India, the Cosmohub provides a rich, immersive experience to tourists, combining local culture and the amazing dark skies of the Himalayas. Visitors can expect a guided tour of the 700-year old monastery, a star-gazing session, and a visitor’s centre providing information about our Universe as well as the cultural astronomy of the region. Tourists can also enjoy gastronomical delights with locally sourced, farm-fresh Ladakhi cuisine. The ultimate aim is to benefit the local community by leveraging humanity’s fascination with the cosmos.

Astrostays is one of the OAD’s Flagship projects run in partnership with the Global Himalayan Expedition and Mountain Homestays.

A DESIGN MANUAL FOR ASTROTOURISM EXPERIENCES

The OAD European Regional Office published the English version of “A Design Manual For Astro-tourism Experiences”, an astrotourism manual that offers guidance and knowledge on improving the quality, appeal, and diversity of the astrotourism experiences that may be designed and implemented in different local settings. It is primarily aimed at owners, managers, or decision-makers of institutions that offer astronomical tourism experiences today, including tourism enterprises, municipal observatories, scientific observatories, etc. The manual is also for entrepreneurs who want to venture into this promising sector. This astrotourism manual is an adaptation from the original developed by VERDE Ltda., as part of the project Astrotourismo Chile and funded by Corfo.

FLAGSHIP 2

ASTRONOMY FOR PEACE, DIPLOMACY AND GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP

This flagship aims to use the inspiring potential of astronomy to stimulate a sense of tolerance and common humanity. The beauty and scale of the universe can induce a 'universal' perspective which can influence how people interact with their fellow human beings and our planet.

ASTRONOMY FOR MENTAL HEALTH

OAD's Astronomy for Mental Health project aims to explore how the inspirational and cultural aspects of astronomy can help improve mental well-being of vulnerable groups, working in collaboration with astronomers, psychologists, mental health professionals, social workers and other specialists. The project team published several comprehensive blogs on mental health and organised a virtual public session in March 2022. The European Regional Office coordinates the related

'Pale Blue Dot' project that uses the perspective of astronomy to promote global citizenship and solidarity.

To collaborate, please send an email to mentalhealth@astro4dev.org or submit an interest through OAD's Collaboration Gateway.

FLAGSHIP 3

ASTRONOMY KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS FOR DEVELOPMENT

This flagship focuses on the use of knowledge and skills used in astronomy to tackle development challenges. This includes methods, techniques widely used in the field including data handling, data analysis, machine learning as well as the necessary compute facilities.

BIG DATA HACKATHONS

Under this project, hackathon events have been implemented in partnership with DARA (Development in Africa with Radio Astronomy) Big Data and the Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy (IDIA). The hackathons aim to provide exposure to skills such as data science and machine learning that are commonly used in astronomy, and provide participants with the confidence to pursue studies or careers in the field of data science going forward. The events also feature talks by local experts in the field, both from industry and academia, in order to provide participants with an overview of data science and its many applications.

Hackathon events have been held in SKA African partner countries Zambia, Ghana, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, and Mauritius as well as two pan-African events held online, one

of which was an all-female event. The hackathon projects are designed to provide participants with hands-on experience in working with real-world data and can be either astronomy or development-related in nature.

All hackathon projects are available via the DARA Big Data and Hack4Dev GitHub repositories, both for those who have been unable to attend an event, and individuals or groups who may be interested in organising their own hackathon event. Additional resources such as the requirements and guidelines to hold a hackathon, as well as tutor guidelines and tutor training videos, have also been made available on the OAD's website.

EVENTS & MEETINGS

IAU OFFICES FAMILY MEETING

The IAU co-hosts four offices around the world – the Office for Astronomy Outreach (OAO) in Japan, the Office for Young Astronomers (OYA) virtually, the Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) in South Africa, and the Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE) in Germany. Each office has its own mandate (outreach, training, development, education) but there is inevitable overlap among these domains. The IAU Centre for the Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky from Satellite Constellation Interference was recently launched in June 2022.

The IAU Offices Family Meeting was planned as a forum to discuss topics of interest for all IAU offices and benefit from synergies. The meeting was open to the networks of all the offices, including the National Astronomy Education Coordinators (NAEC), National Outreach Coordinators (NOC), Regional Office of Astronomy for Development (ROAD) and Language Expertise Centres of the OAD (LOAD). It was organised by the IAU Office of Astronomy for Education with support from the other offices. Participants were invited to propose discussion topics in advance, resulting in a participant-driven meeting with dynamic and lively sessions. More than 30 sessions were organised over the three days with plenty of debate and discussion. Topics included: Archival data for education, Remote teaching and outreach, Decolonising Astronomy Outreach and Education, Monitoring and evaluation, Astronomy education in low-income communities, Astrotourism, Astronomy and careers, and more.

IN CONVERSATION WITH ASSAF – 'ASTRONOMY IN AFRICA'

Kevin Govender & Vanessa McBride from the OAD talked to the Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf) on 'Astronomy in Africa'. The talk explored how Africa has become a global player in this field, and what this means for how the world sees Africa. It touched on the exciting science being done in Africa; the incredible infrastructure both current and planned; the vibrant and growing network of African astronomers; and the opportunities presented by events like the General Assembly of the International Astronomical Union.

AERAP 2021: ASTRONOMY AS A UNIQUE ENGINE FOR EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT

The African Astronomical Society (AfAS) and the OAD organised a session entitled "Africa-EU Astronomy Collaborations: Towards the First IAU-General Assembly on the African Continent in 2024, and Beyond" at the Africa-Europe Science and Innovation Summit. This special session was an opportunity for interactions between existing and potential Africa-EU collaborators to stimulate and explore mutually beneficial opportunities that may arise specifically in the lead up towards the IAU-GA in 2024.

UN GA76 SCIENCE SUMMIT: ASTRONOMY TO ADVANCE SDGs

The Office of Astronomy for Development, led by its European Regional Office, organised a session on Astronomy to Advance SDGs at the United Nations General Assembly Science Summit. The UN GA76 Science Summit, held online from 14 - 30 September, aimed to raise awareness of the role and contribution of science to the attainment of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. It demonstrated initiatives that provide models for global science mechanisms and activities in support of the SDGs. The event was organised under the auspices of Intelligence in Science (ISC) and Africa Europe Radio Astronomy Platform (AERAP).

REGIONAL OFFICES

ANDEAN ROAD

- The Andean Region website is being improved to enable better communication with the community. <https://andean.astro4dev.org/>
- The Office has several events planned in 2023: (1) Third Workshop of Astronomy in the Andes, to be held in Bolivia, (2) First Andean Meeting on Astrotourism, to be held in Ecuador

ARAB ROAD/LOAD

- The Arab regional office participated in hundreds of activities during this period. This included organising astronomy lectures for students, supervision of research students, and workshops.
- The Arab Regional Office & Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences, in cooperation with the Ministry of Education, organised six teacher training workshops (Jordan, Syria, Tunisia) with the participation of more than 150 people from 15 Arab countries.

CHINESE & EAST ASIAN LOAD/ROAD

- The East Asian and Chinese Language Office is coordinating an innovative forum "Talking about Astronomy and People, Empowering Future Development".

EAST AFRICAN ROAD

- The 6th East Africa Astronomical Society workshop was conducted in May 2021 in hybrid mode at the University of Dodoma, Tanzania. The EAASW was organised by the Open University of Tanzania, the University of Dodoma and East Africa ROAD.
- The IAU symposium 'Dark sky and astronomical heritage in boosting Astro-tourism around the globe' will be organised by the East African Regional Office and the Ethiopian Space Science and Technology Institute in Ethiopia in 2023.

EUROPEAN ROAD

- The European Office implemented the EU-funded SKIES project, with skills training workshops in Europe and South Africa;
- They are coordinating a special session at the European Astronomical Society annual meeting titled "Astronomy for Development."

NORTH AMERICAN ROAD

- The Regional Office published its strategic plan that is being translated to French and Spanish. <https://naroad.astro4dev.org/strategic-plan/>
- The first NA-ROAD project will be 'Making Astronomy Accessible for All'. This effort will include professional development workshops on the use of Afterglow Access Software. This software resulted from the IDATA project (You

can access AgA software at <https://www.idataport.org/>, click on the Resources tab), and is browser-based and is accessible free of charge. In addition, the software includes features that make astronomical image analysis more accessible to the blind and visually impaired.

PORTUGUESE LOAD

- A webinar was organised in commemoration of the International Day of Portuguese Language, with participation of representatives of 4 PLOAD countries: Brazil, Cape Verde, Mozambique and Portugal.
- "OruMbya" project, led by institutions in Brazil and supported by the OAD, was featured during the UN GA76 Science Summit.

SOUTHERN AFRICAN ROAD

- The Southern African Regional Office has been preparing and fundraising for hosting the Pan African School for Emerging Astronomers which will be held in Livingstone, Zambia from 10 to 15 October 2022. Call for applications for the summer school: <https://www.paseafrica.org/pasea-2022>.
- Astrolab training workshop was conducted remotely in 2021. In-person workshops have been planned for Zambia, Ethiopia and Nigeria in 2022. The Las Cumbres Observatory has granted telescope time for education purposes following the successful implementation of the project in the preceding year.
- The MOU for continuation of hosting the Southern African ROAD by the Copperbelt University was renewed in October 2021 for a period of five years.

SOUTH WEST AND CENTRAL ASIAN ROAD

- The South West and Central Asian Office carried out several activities related to the host institution's 75th Anniversary; approaches have been made with new countries in the region.

SOUTH EAST ASIAN ROAD

- The South East Asian Office continued to drive several activities related to expanding the reach to other countries in the region.
- A proposal for a 2023 IAU symposium has been submitted.

WEST AFRICAN ROAD

- An All Sky Survey in collaboration with North American ROAD is ongoing with participation by students from various West African ROAD countries. The project is centered on night sky mapping using the Stone Edge Astronomy Observatory Telescope in Chicago remotely.
- Development of Africa through Radio Astronomy (DARA) practical training took place at the Ghana Radio Astronomy Observatory for participants from Ghana, Kenya, Namibia, Zambia and Botswana in July 2021.

REGIONAL OFFICES

PARTNERSHIPS

The OAD works with a number of institutions across the world that help us achieve our goals. If you want to know more, or your organisation is interested in exploring a partnership, contact us at info@astro4dev.org.

OAD COLLABORATION GATEWAY

In December 2021, the OAD launched a collaboration gateway with a view to support interactions between astronomy and other disciplines or projects, where the goal is creating a positive impact on sustainable development. The collaboration gateway is a natural evolution for the flagship projects of the OAD, and provides a space for forging new partnerships and engaging across cultural and disciplinary boundaries. There are two ways of interacting with the collaboration gateway: either through browsing existing content and going on to execute a project, or by proposing a project and generating onboarding material for astronomers and others who may want to collaborate. Even the sky is not the limit when it comes to the types of projects that might benefit from collaboration! Cross-disciplinary research projects and optimisation problems are well-suited to the collaboration gateway, but it also lends itself to small business development and on-the-ground project support.

VIRTUAL OBSERVATORY – OAD SPECIAL GRANT

The OAD and the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) have joined forces to bring together our complementary resources and expertise to advance the application of astronomical data and/or technology use in different areas of society, most notably for education, development and public outreach. To this end, a special grant is being offered to support the development of Virtual Observatory (VO) tools in an undergraduate teaching context.

WARWICK ASTRONOMY KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE

The Warwick Astronomy Knowledge Exchange programme (WAKE) is a collaboration between the Warwick University Astronomy Group, OAD and its Regional Offices, and the Warwick Ethnic Minorities in Physics Network. The programme aims to increase the diversity of people applying for opportunities at Warwick especially from countries under-represented in the field of astronomy. With the help of the OAD's 11 Regional Offices, WAKE selected and invited six participants from countries with under-represented astronomy programmes to go to Warwick University.

DARA BIG DATA - OAD INFRASTRUCTURE CALL

The OAD, in partnership with DARA Big Data (funded by the Newton Fund), launched a call for proposals for computing infrastructure targeted at Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the SKA Partner Countries (Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia and Zambia). This call sought to help HEIs build on their existing computing resources, which will in turn benefit students and researchers, in line with the objectives of DARA Big Data.

DEVELOPMENT OF AFRICA THROUGH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA) is a joint UK – South Africa Newton funded project that uses radio astronomy training to develop high level technical skills in young graduates. The partnership is an implementation of the astronomy-for-development concept and involves collaboration at both strategy and project evaluation levels.

DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA WITH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA) BIG DATA PROJECT is funded by the United Kingdom Newton Fund via the Science and Technologies Facilities Council, and aims to develop big data skills using radio astronomy in SKA African partner countries. Through a partnership with DARA Big Data, the OAD hosts a fellow, Dr Nikhita Madhanpall, who is working on hackathons that expose students and young people to big data and machine learning in both astronomy and development-related contexts.

AFRICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (AFAS) – The African Astronomical Society was established in 2011, and is the voice of professional astronomy on the African continent. The purpose of the partnership between the OAD and AfAS is to provide and maximise a network of astronomy practitioners on the African continent, to respond rapidly to special events and to work together to implement and safeguard the legacy of the first General Assembly of the International Astronomical Union to be held on the African continent in 2024.

INTERNATIONAL VIRTUAL OBSERVATORY ALLIANCE (IVOA) – The IVOA was formed in June 2002 and aims to facilitate international coordination and collaboration in tools, systems and organisational structures for astronomical archives. The IVOA now comprises 20 Virtual Observatory programmes from Argentina, Armenia, Australia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Europe, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Italy, Japan, Russia, South Africa, Spain, Ukraine, the United Kingdom, and the United States and an inter-governmental organisation (ESA). The purpose of the partnership is to bring together the complementary resources and expertise of the IVOA and the OAD to advance the application of astronomical data and/or technology use in different areas of society, most notably for education, development and public outreach.

INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF BASIC SCIENCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (IYBSSD)

- An agreement was reached with the IYBSSD to list all OAD Regional Offices as "IYBSSD Nodes". The IAU is one of the official partners for IYBSSD through an MOU between the IAU and the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics (who is the coordinating organisation).

INTER-UNIVERSITY CENTRE FOR ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS (IUCAA)

India is one of the leading research institutes in astronomy/astrophysics globally. IUCAA also has a well-renowned programme of public outreach and education (SciPop). Since our establishment, OAD and IUCAA have enjoyed close ties. This partnership paves way for specific collaborations in capacity development along education, development and outreach.

ROYAL ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (RAS)

UK encourages and promotes the study of astronomy, solar-system science, geophysics and closely related branches of science. The RAS and OAD have partnered to establish or nurture research, educational and/or development related collaborations between the UK and countries where astronomy research is not well established.

SPACE GENERATION ADVISORY COUNCIL (SGAC)

in support of the United Nations Programme on Space Applications is a global non-governmental, non-profit (US 501(c)3) organisation and network that aims to represent university students and young space professionals ages 18-35 to the United Nations, space agencies, industry, and academia. Both OAD and SGAC have common goals in strengthening global networks in space and astronomy and developing capacity in STEM fields.

FINANCIAL INFORMATION

COMPLIANCE

The OAD operates within the financial systems and policies of the NRF, which comply with South African national legislation. Compliance of the OAD's financial transactions to the relevant policies is tested through annual audits of the SAAO and NRF. The OAD financial year (April to March) is different as compared to the implementation of funded projects (calendar year), and long-term special projects or grants (which can be multi-year).

OPERATIONS

For the duration of the IAU-NRF agreement, the OAD receives an annual core income from the DSI/NRF and the IAU, all administered through the NRF. Since the renewed IAU-NRF agreement in 2015, the DSI/NRF provides R1,500,000 per year with an annual inflationary increase of 6%, plus the salary and associated costs of a full time OAD astronomer. The IAU provides a fixed amount of €70,000 per year, plus the salary and associated costs of a part-time fundraiser employed by the IAU. In addition the IAU funds the annual call for proposals (€120,000 per year). Since 2016, these project grants have been paid directly from the IAU in Paris. The total allocation for 2022 projects was €109,822, with the remainder reserved for contingencies such as top-ups required due to unforeseen COVID-related circumstances

INCOME

For the 2021–2022 financial year, the DSI/NRF provided R3,498,000 and the IAU provided R1,270,721 (total core income of R4,768,721). In addition the OAD received project income from DARA Big Data totalling R445,125. There was also a carryover of R628,740 due mainly to unfilled positions over the past few years. At the end of the year there was still a surplus of R833,956, which will be fully utilised in the next financial years on the multi-year flagship projects.

EXPENDITURE

The 2021-2022 financial year, for the second time, shows the effects of the pandemic, with almost no travel and meetings. This meant that much of the budgeted travel and conference costs were unspent. The OAD redirected these funds to special grants for the three flagship projects and remote fellowships. The largest expenses for the financial year were therefore salaries (R2,628,696) and project funding (R1,890,829). Other operational costs were much lower in comparison due to the work-from-home and travel restrictions for almost the entire financial year.

science & innovation

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